

Sealing the End : Root End Surgery for a Persistent Periapical Pathosis : A Case Report

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Abstract

Surgical root canal therapy, or apicoectomy, is indicated when non surgical re-treatment is unsuccessful or impractical. The procedure involves resection of approximately 3 mm of the root apex, removal of periapical pathology, preparation of a root end cavity, and placement of a retrograde filling to establish a hermetic apical seal. Various root end filling materials, including amalgam, gutta-percha, zinc oxide-eugenol cements, glass ionomers, and bioceramics, have been employed; however, mineral trioxide aggregate (MTA) has emerged as the material of choice due to its superior sealing ability, biocompatibility, and capacity to promote regenerative healing. This case report presents a case of a 22-year-old male with a persistent periapical lesion associated with tooth 21. Following unsuccessful non surgical management, apicoectomy was performed with root end filling using MTA. Postoperative evaluation revealed uneventful healing, histopathological confirmation of periapical granuloma, and radiographic evidence of bone regeneration at 5 months. This case highlights the effectiveness of apicoectomy as a predictable treatment modality in managing refractory periapical pathology, with success rates exceeding 85–90% when combined with modern microsurgical techniques and biocompatible materials.

Introduction

Surgical root canal therapy is often indicated when non surgical retreatment has failed or cannot be performed. Surgical root canal therapy usually involves resecting a portion of the root apex and preparing and filling a cavity in the root end. The term apicoectomy defined as the surgical removal of the apical portion of a tooth root, along with any associated periapical pathologic tissue, followed by the preparation and placement of a retrograde filling to seal the root canal system from the periapical aspect. The principal objective is to seal the canal system at the apical foramen from the periradicular tissues. To do this, it is necessary to resect the apical part of the root to gain access to the root canal. The aim of resection is to present the surface of the root so that the apical limit of the canal can be visually examined and to provide access for retrograde cavity preparation. Approximately 3 mm of root is removed which includes almost all lateral canals. Root end resection must be an adjunct measure to orthograde root treatment for two reasons. Firstly, there is very little chance of being able to seal all the lateral communications between the canal and the periodontal ligament with a retrograde root filling technique. Secondly, the area of

root filling material exposed will be greater and the long-term success affected, because all root filling materials are, to some extent, irritant to the tissues.^{1,2}

Retrograde filling materials such as amalgam, gutta percha, zinc-oxide eugenol cements (IRM, SuperEBA), Glass ionomer cements, composite resins, compomers, diaket, Ceramicrete, Bio-aggregate, Bioceramics etc. are commonly used in endodontic surgical procedures. All of these materials have been shown to be compatible with tissue cicatrisation and the reconstitution of periradicular alveolar bone, but none of them is able to induce cementum formation and full periodontal ligament repair. Mineral trioxide aggregate (MTA), a calcium silicate based material developed by the modification of Portland cement, has been introduced to address this problem and has shown good biocompatibility and sealing properties. This material permits a full regenerative healing and can be considered as the material of choice in endodontic surgery. In addition, the

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sealing properties of MTA are not affected by moisture during treatment.³

Surgical Technique Overview

Although the details vary depending on the tooth location, root morphology, and surgeon preference, the general sequence of an apicoectomy includes:

Preoperative assessment : Detailed clinical and radiographic examination, evaluation of the lesion, root anatomy, and proximity to anatomical landmarks.

Local anesthesia and flap design : Incision planning to ensure optimal access, minimal trauma, and primary closure potential. Common flap designs include triangular, rectangular, or sub-marginal incisions.

Osteotomy : Removal of overlying cortical bone to expose the root apex and periapical lesion.

Periapical Curettage : Complete removal of pathological tissue for histopathological examination.

Root end resection : Resection of 3 mm of the apical root portion to eliminate most apical ramifications and lateral canals.

Root end preparation : Ultrasonic tips are often used to prepare a class I cavity, centered along the long axis of the canal.

Retrograde filling : Placement of a biocompatible material such as MTA or Biodentine to create a hermetic apical seal.

Flap repositioning and suturing: Ensuring tension free closure and optimal healing.

Postoperative care : Analgesia, antimicrobial measures if indicated, and follow-up assessments.

Case Report

Patient History and Examination

A 22 year old male presented to the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics in Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College and research Centre, Ghaziabad with a chief complaint of occasional swelling and mild tenderness in the upper front region for the past six months.

Extraoral examination was unremarkable. Intraoral examination revealed the crown on tooth 21 to be intact, with no mobility or periodontal pockets. Palpation elicited mild tenderness over the labial mucosa apical to the tooth. Percussion produced slight discomfort. Thermal and electric pulp tests were negative for the tooth, as expected.

Periapical radiograph revealed tooth 21 with a large periapical lesion approximately 6 mm in diameter. No sinus tract was observed clinically. (Fig 1)

Fig 1: Pre-operative Radiograph

Treatment Plan

Access opening was done using high speed airrotor and working length was determined using a 10k file. Biomechanical preparation was performed and calcium hydroxide dressing was placed for 1 week. No change in periapical lesion was noticed even after intracanal medicament placement. Obturation was done using lateral condensation technique and surgical endodontic treatment was considered. (Fig 2)

Fig 2 : Obturation of 21

Surgical Procedure

After obtaining written informed consent, the procedure was performed under local anesthesia (2% lignocaine with 1:80,000 adrenaline). A full-thickness mucoperiosteal flap was raised using a sulcular incision with vertical releasing incisions adjacent to tooth 21 (Fig 3). The labial cortical bone overlying the lesion was removed using a round bur under copious irrigation to create an osteotomy window. (Fig 4)

Fig 3 : Flap Reflected

Fig 4 : Bony Window

Granulation tissue surrounding the root apex was curetted (Fig 6) and stored in 10% formalin for histopathological examination. Approximately 3 mm of the root apex was resected perpendicular to the long axis of the tooth using a tapered fissure bur(Fig 5). Ultrasonic tips were used to prepare a 3 mm deep root end cavity centered along the canal (Fig 7). The cavity was irrigated with sterile saline and dried with paper points.

Mineral Trioxide Aggregate (ProRoot MTA, Dentsply) was placed incrementally into the cavity and compacted to achieve a dense, flush fill (Fig 8). The surgical site was irrigated with saline, the flap repositioned, and sutured with 4-0 silk sutures (Fig 11). A sterile pressure pack was applied.

Fig 5 : Root End Resection

Fig 6 : Curettage of the Granulation Tissue

Fig 7: Retrograde Cavity Preparation using Ultrasonic

Fig 8 : Retrograde Cavity filled with MTA

Fig 9 : Retrograde Cavity Prepared

Fig 10 : Retrograde Cavity filled by MTA

Fig 11: Suturing Done

Fig 12 : 1 Months follow up

Fig 13 : 3 Months follow up up

Fig 14 : 5 Months follow up

Postoperative Care

The patient was prescribed antibiotics and analgesic every 6 hourly for 7 days and chlorhexidine mouth rinse twice daily for one week. He was instructed to avoid mechanical trauma to the surgical site. Sutures were removed after 7 days, with uneventful soft tissue healing.

Follow Up and Outcome

Histopathological examination of the excised tissue confirmed a periapical granuloma. At the 5-month review (Fig 14), the patient reported no symptoms, and radiographs showed partial bone fill, with restoration of normal periodontal ligament space and lamina dura.

Discussion

This case illustrates the role of apicoectomy in managing persistent periapical pathology in situations where non surgical retreatment is not feasible. The maxillary anterior region offers favorable access, and the use of microsurgical techniques with MTA as a root-end filling material contributed to the predictable outcome observed.

MTA is composed of a hydrophilic powder mainly composed of calcium oxide. The high level of the apical seal of MTA, compared to that of other materials has been confirmed by several studies. The main advantages of the material are: biocompatibility, osteo-induction and regenerative potential, MTA did not induce cytotoxicity or inflammatory response of the body. Some of its

disadvantages are: difficult manipulative and slow hardening, which may be the reason for the penetration and also surface disintegration and loss of marginal adaptation. Some authors have reported that the success in retrograde filling with MTA is higher in comparison with dental amalgam while others come to the conclusion that both materials used in the retrograde filling have similar clinical outcomes.^{4,5}

MTA is known for its superior sealing ability, biocompatibility, and promotion of periapical healing. Resection of at least 3 mm of the root apex is recommended to remove most apical ramifications and lateral canals that may harbor bacteria. Success rates for modern apicoectomy exceed 85–90% when performed under magnification with appropriate materials.⁵

Conclusion

Apicoectomy provides an effective means of preserving teeth affected by persistent periapical lesions when orthograde retreatment is not practical. The present case demonstrates favorable clinical and radiographic outcomes following surgical apicoectomy in a maxillary anterior tooth, underscoring the importance of meticulous surgical technique, appropriate case selection, and use of biocompatible materials.

References

1. Saxena P. Biocompatibility of root end filling materials: recent update Restor Dent Endod. 2013 Aug; 38 (3): 119–127
2. Bhagwat SA, Hegde S, Mandke LP. An investigation into the effectiveness of periapical surgery with Biodentine™ used as a root end filling alone or in combination with demineralized freeze dried bone allograft and plasma rich fibrin: A 6 months follow-up of 17 cases. Endodontology 2016; 28 :11-7.
3. William Ha . The properties of Mineral Trioxide Aggregate and how it can be manipulated. Australian Society of endodontology. 2015.
4. Silva W J D, Souza P H C, Rosa E A R, Cury A A D B, Rached R N Rev. odonto ciênc. 2010; 25 (4): 386-390
5. Xavier C B, Weismann R, Oliveira M G, Demarco F F, Pozza D H. Root end filling materials: apical microleakage and marginal adaptation. J Endod. 2005 Jul ; 31(7) : 539-42